

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report lists the selected model developments that were tested based on input from WP5 and WP6, and will draw conclusions on their potential for further improving the SR-ESMs.

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WP3

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Executive summary

We list selected model developments that go beyond sensitivities to spatial resolution and draw conclusions on their potential for further improving the SR-ESMs in nextGEMS, ICON (Hohenegger et al., 2023) and IFS-FESOM (Rackow et al., 2025). These developments are also been taken over by the initiative led by the European Commission Destination Earth, since IFS-FESOM and ICON are two of the models underpinning the [Climate Adaptation Digital Twin](#). We cover parameterised aspects (turbulent mixing in atmosphere and ocean, tuning of micro-physics) and developments aimed at expanding the scope of what is being modelled (simple aerosol models, biogeochemistry components, and novel applications arising from Knowledge Coproduction activities). We close by presenting new 30-year long nextGEMS simulations at 9 km resolution that have been performed over the observational period, as well as new ICON and IFS-FESOM simulations at 2.5 km over several years in total. These tests and simulations have been possible thanks to computing resources provided by the German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ) and, to a lesser extent, LUMI EuroHPC.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP3	Relevance in this deliverable?
To complete Cycle 3 (Development) simulations (O1).	yes
To finalize the configuration (including associated output and data management requirements) of SR-ESMs for the production simulations (O1).	no
To perform present day and future projections (i.e., production simulations). (O1/O2)	yes
To organize and curate simulation output for sustainable access beyond the completion of NextGEMS. (O1/O2/O3)	no
To support the four themes in exploring extensions of SR-ESMs to address additional application needs and testing proposed model improvements. (O1/O2/O3)	yes

Synergies

This deliverable lists selected model developments that were tested, based on input from WP5 and WP6. We also draw conclusions on their potential for further improving the storm-resolving Earth System Models (SR-ESMs).

1 Introduction

During the development of the project there have been numerous model developments and test simulations to explore extended capabilities of the SR-ESMs participating in the project. i.e. ICON and IFS-FESOM. In this deliverable we show the main developments and their potential impact in future simulations by SR-ESMs. We first document in Section 2 experiments that we carried at coarser resolutions than the kilometer-scale. Then, we split the developments into the two following sections, with Section 3 documenting those aimed to improve or refine already existing processes in the models, and Section 4 showing the developments that aim to expand the capabilities of what SR-ESMs can model. In addition, we also document additional simulations that were performed in the project on top of the production simulations. These additional simulations mostly aimed to either produce simulation data on past observable periods (Section 5), or to explore very high spatial resolutions of up to 2.5km (Section 6).

2 Experiments at coarser resolution

Recently, global tracer-mass fixers were activated in the IFS in order to address water non-conservation and the associated atmospheric energy leak. In short, the tracer-mass fixer makes sure that each water species in the atmosphere is globally conserved (accounting for water exchanges with the surface) before and after the model dynamics are computed.

Building on this work, we performed a hierarchy of additional experiments at different spatial resolutions to determine whether water conservation properties, energy conservation, and TOA energy imbalance was resolution-dependent for the IFS. For this, we performed short 12-day forecasts at resolutions of TCo399 (28 km), TCo1279 (9 km), TCo2559 (4.4 km), and TCo3999 (2.8 km), while also testing different convection configurations (default deep convection, deep-convection disabled, and reduced cloud-base mass flux). Scaled column water imbalances remained small for all experiments. The atmospheric energy imbalance also remained generally small, with some resolution dependence, changing from $+0.1 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ at TCo399 to around -0.3 W m^{-2} at higher resolutions. Net top-of-atmosphere radiation generally stayed within $\pm 0.5 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ of the observational CERES reference across resolutions, with variation attributable to the resolution-dependence of the TOA tuning.

An additional idealized experiment was produced with IFS in order to distinguish the role of high-resolution surface information from high-resolution orography. This experiment was run at 9 km, with the respective orography information, but replacing all land surface characteristics (land use/ land cover, vegetation properties, soil types, e.t.c.) by coarser resolution fields, containing information only of down to 28 km for 13 months. To keep as much comparability as possible, the SSTs and sea ice from a standard nextGEMS simulation at 9 km (IFS-NEMO in Cycle 3) were used to force the ocean conditions. Results showed that the daily maximum sub-grid variability of land surface temperature is partly explained by spatial variability of surface information, e.g., land cover and vegetation. This was further shown in the report on the implemented revised land surface information in IFS (D8.2).

3 Model developments aimed at improving parameterised aspects of SR-ESMs

3.1 Turbulent mixing in the ocean and atmosphere

3.1.1 Atmosphere

The nextGEMS project allowed us to assess the representation of the atmospheric boundary layer in kilometer-scale Earth system models, and to compare two different modeling approaches. ICON applies a minimal set of parameterizations, using in the atmosphere only turbulence, cloud microphysics, and radiation schemes (Hohenegger et al., 2023). Conversely, the IFS operates as a weather forecasting model, incorporating years of model tuning, and employs sophisticated parameterization schemes for several processes, including deep and shallow convection (Rackow et al., 2025). Regarding specifically the turbulence parametrization, ICON uses the Smagorinsky model (Smagorinsky, 1963), while IFS uses the eddy–diffusivity mass–flux scheme (Köhler et al., 2011).

The main result is that both model strategies successfully represent the main features of the atmospheric boundary layer, which was an open question at the beginning of the project given that grid spacings of 2.5 km to 5 km are still larger than the boundary-layer height. For the evaluation, we considered trade cumulus and subtropical stratocumulus regimes. Results have been thoroughly reported in the corresponding deliverables (D6.1, D6.2, D7.1, D7.4) and the study of the subtropical stratocumulus regimes has already been published (Nowak et al., 2025).

For illustration purposes, we briefly discuss here the trade cumulus regime. Figure 1 shows the vertical structure of the atmospheric boundary layer corresponding to the EUREC⁴A field campaign (Stevens et al., 2021). The simulated potential temperature and specific humidity profiles are roughly consistent with the observed vertical structure. Both observations and simulations show a moist boundary layer, a dry free troposphere, and a well-mixed sub-cloud layer extending to around 600 m. However, there are discrepancies. On average, the simulations depict a moist layer that is slightly cooler and drier than the observations. IFS simulations with the shallow convection scheme represent a moister and warmer cloud layer (900–1500 m) compared to ICON, in better agreement with observations. However, IFS with the shallow convection scheme disabled resembles the ICON configuration more closely, and both simulations represent an even drier cloud layer. This indicates that, although the main features of the boundary layer are captured at kilometer-scale resolution, quantitative details still depend on the turbulence and convection parametrization.

At the same time, however, this sensitivity to the turbulence and convection parametrization indicates the potential to use them to tune the climate model. This was used several times to control the energy balance at the top of the atmosphere. IFS and ICON offer different options. The former has more flexibility given that it retains more elements in the parametrization, in particular, the shallow and the deep convection parts. The challenge is the interaction between these different elements. In ICON, the tuning was done by means of the stability function. This caused challenges to disentangle the effects on the trade cumulus and on the stratocumulus.

Figure 1: Atmospheric profiles of potential temperature (left) and specific humidity (right) averaged over the EUREC⁴A-Circle from simulations using ICON and IFS models. Observations (black), ICON (green), and IFS-NEMO with deep and shallow convection schemes (yellow), with deep convection disabled (orange), and with both deep and shallow convection disabled (red) are shown.

Looking into the future, one option would be to consider the Leonard terms in the subgrid scale models, following large-eddy simulation and promising results in NICAM (Takasuka et al., 2024).

Work has also been done to further develop the parameterisations in the nextGEMS models. Here, we wish to mention a development of the Smagorinsky sub-grid scale mixing scheme employed in the ICON model. The mixing length (Δ), or filter width, of the Smagorinsky scheme is defined using the grid spacings. It is typically the same in all directions (isotropic), e.g. $\Delta = (\Delta x \Delta y \Delta z)^{1/3}$, which works well when the horizontal and vertical grid spacings are similar, i.e. close to isotropic. A particular challenge with the Smagorinsky scheme in a storm-resolving model environment is the substantial difference between horizontal and vertical turbulent mixing due to large differences in horizontal and vertical grid spacing, often several orders of magnitude different. Using an isotropic Smagorinsky scheme gives too strong vertical mixing and too weak horizontal mixing. This can have particularly strong influence on clouds in which strong vertical gradients exist such as stratocumulus cases. An anisotropic version of the Smagorinsky model, in which mixing length is different in the horizontal than in the vertical direction, was tested in idealized stratocumulus simulations (Fig. 2) modeled by the University of Warsaw Lagrangian Cloud Model (UWLCM). Shifting to an anisotropic formulation leads to a qualitatively different simulation, with formation of a closed-cell structure similar to that observed in stratocumulus clouds (Fig. 2, right). This new development will have to see further testing in other cases and, eventually, in a global model setting.

Figure 2: Liquid water path in two simulations by the University of Warsaw Lagrangian Cloud Model (UWLCM) with isotropic (left) and anisotropic (right) Smagorinski sub-grid scale mixing. The resolution of the simulations is 2 km horizontally and 20 m vertically.

3.1.2 Ocean

Results from WP6 and WP7 have shown that details of ocean mixed-layer (ML) schemes do not seem to majorly impact long-standing atmospheric biases - fundamental biases like the double ITCZ still remain. Thus, we adopted an alternative approach and developed Veropt: a Bayesian optimization tool for ocean models that, via an automated parameter-tuning algorithm, optimizes the whole set of uncertain parameters in one go. The current version can utilize the LUMI GPUs and delivers an optimized 9-dimensional parameter space for a 1 degree ocean model in a week (Mrozowska et al., 2024). Until the end of the project we expect to be able to apply Veropt to fully coupled Fortran-based climate models, which should allow us to reduce the double ITCZ biases known from most climate models substantially. Provided that we will be supplied with dedicated computing resources (requests are pending), Veropt can then be applied to SR-ESMs like ICON as well.

Standard parameter optimization for ESMs often relies on expert knowledge in order to decide which of the model parameters most affect the desired outcome (here: c_k in TKE is modified to affect tropical precipitation). Integrations with different parameter values are then performed and outcomes are compared (Bastin et al., 2025). This is time consuming and important parameters may be overlooked. However, simply trying all possible combinations of all parameter values is too expensive. Thus, in Veropt an initial set of random parameter choices is used to create an estimate of the topology of the model error. Based on this topology new parameter values are chosen, and the process is repeated until the model error converges to a minimum. The success of this method does depend on the real topology of the model error (see Mrozowska et al., 2024 for the technical details), but our present results suggest that for climate models this method is a promising way forward.

A single LUMI GPU node has 8 GPUs, each one can host a 1x1 degree ocean model integration. After 20 iterations, each one being 32 simulations in parallel using the ocean model Veros (<https://veros.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>), we were able to improve significantly the ML depth, through an unexpected combination of 3 bulk-flux coefficients, 2 parameters of the implemen-

Figure 3: Zonal average of annual mean mixed layer depth for the observations (solid black line), the default model configuration (dotted line) and the simulations with the 26 best parameter sets (red). Note that the best sets reduce the MLD in high latitudes and reduce it in low latitudes, both being an improvement.

tation of thickness diffusion (Eden and Greatbatch, 2008), and 4 parameters of the TKE scheme (Fig. 3). Apart from MLD errors, the loss function contained the strengths of AMOC and ACC, as well as the depth of the 18C isotherm to avoid that MLD improvements are achieved at the cost of other key model states. In particular, the improvement in the Southern Ocean alleviates a long-standing bias of ocean general circulation models (OGCMs), which suggests that longstanding biases in coupled configurations can be tackled with our approach as well. These experiments are a proof of concept and show that Bayesian optimization is a highly sample-efficient method, and that could therefore be potentially used to address typical issues such as the double ITCZ in SR-ESMs.

3.2 Microphysics

With regards to microphysics, the IFS model development for nextGEMS focused on rain evaporation. To achieve more physical rain evaporation at high resolutions, we (1) removed an artificial threshold on relative humidity that prohibits rain evaporation when relative humidity is high, (2) added a sub-grid assumption that precipitation falls into the moistest part of the grid box, using the sub-grid humidity variability assumption in the Tiedtke cloud scheme (Tiedtke, 1993), (3) ensured a proportional reduction of precipitation area fraction when rain evaporates and (4) returned the resulting rain evaporation to get realistic results. While results are realistic in terms of mean state biases, further work will be needed to improve the realism of cold pools. A model intercomparison study with IFS, ICON, and NICAM has shown that while all models underesti-

mate cold pool intensity, IFS shows the most significant biases (Takasuka et al., 2025, in prep.). Ongoing model development aims at addressing this problem by introducing a double-moment representation of microphysics.

As an alternative model development strategy, instead of trying to improve specific elements of a parameterization by improving physical realism, algorithmic tuning can be used. Algorithmic tuning was also explored for uncertain microphysics parameters together with all other parameters that play key roles in how the model atmosphere behaves (and which are also uncertain in terms of their exact values). Work on the algorithmic tuning is presented in detail in Deliverable D26 (Del. Rel. No. D5.2) "Report on sub-grid scale parametrisations and internal balance" and in the three articles referenced therein. Thus, algorithmic tuning is summarised here very shortly only.

The algorithmic tuning experiments were carried out with simultaneous optimisation of 20 parameters of Open Integrated Forecasting System (OpenIFS). In general, the chosen tuning method exhibits remarkable convergence of the parameters towards more favourable values (Fig. 4). Independent verification of the tuned models showed that algorithmic tuning is able to increase the forecast skill about 0.5-1.0% on average. However, specific model biases may experience even further reductions of up to 20%. The computational cost of tuning the model with this method is equivalent of 10 years continuous simulation.

Algorithmic tuning is certainly beneficial for the deterministic forecast skill, but in terms of ensemble skill, the results are mixed. Model parameters appear to have strong and non-trivial influence on the spread of ensemble forecasts. It appears that algorithmic tuning always leads to improved deterministic forecasts, but the impact on ensemble spread varies apparently randomly from case to case. This can be either beneficial or detrimental depending on the spread-skill relationship of the ensemble forecasting system. A convenient method to measure whether the impact is net positive for the ensemble forecasts is a metric called "filter likelihood score", which demonstrated good capability to differentiate between ensembles having different error and spread levels.

4 Model developments aimed at expanding the scope of what is being modelled

4.1 Simple aerosol models

Aerosols influence Earth's climate directly by scattering or absorbing radiation and indirectly by serving as nuclei for cloud droplets or ice crystals. To perform kilometer-scale (km-scale) simulations with the Earth system model ICON, we developed the one-moment aerosol module HAM-lite. In HAM-lite, aerosols are represented as an ensemble of log-normal modes with prescribed properties. The modes are transported through the atmosphere and are coupled with the turbulence, radiation, and cloud microphysics scheme (Weiss et al., 2024).

To evaluate the aerosol scheme, we performed a year-long simulation at a resolution of 5 km. The aerosols are represented with two pure modes, one composed of dust and one composed

Figure 4: Example of parameter convergence in experiment called "ISP ON 1". The x-axis shows the running number of steps of tuning algorithm, and the y-axis shows the relative parameter values with respect to the default parameter value. The black dots show the parameter values assigned to individual ensemble members, the red lines show the mean value of the parameters, the blue lines show ± 2 standard deviations, and the green lines show the default parameter value (=1 in all cases). The plots are grouped by parameterization scheme.

of sea salt, and two mixed modes, both composed of organic carbon, black carbon, and sulfate. The first mixed mode includes aerosols from wildfire emissions and the second mixed mode includes aerosols from anthropogenic and volcanic emissions. Anthropogenic emissions were taken from CEDS (Hoesly et al., 2018) and wildfire emissions from GFAS (Kaiser et al., 2012). The simulation starts on 20 January 2020.

Figure 5 shows a scene of aerosol burdens on 5 August 2020 at 00:00 UTC. Table 3 shows the aerosol burdens, emissions, lifetimes, and optical depths at 550 nm of our simulation and of the AeroCom phase 3 model intercomparison averaged over the year 2010 (Gliß et al., 2021). Figure 6 shows the optical depth of our simulation and the MODIS-Aqua satellite, i.e., the combined dark target and deep blue product, averaged over five years from 2018 to 2022 (Platnick et al., 2015). Despite the simplicity of our model, our values are comparable to those of the AeroCom intercomparison and the MODIS-Aqua satellite.

Over the next months, we plan to perform additional simulations with different emission scenarios and over different years. These simulations will help us to estimate the radiative forcing of anthropogenic aerosols (Forster et al., 2021) and the contribution of reduced shipping emissions to the surface temperature anomalies in 2022 to 2023 (Gettelman et al., 2024; Goessling et al., 2025). Further exploring how much of the rapid warming in 2023 is due to internal variability, reduced aerosol concentrations, or a possibly emerging positive low-cloud feedback will be crucial for assessing the present and expected future warming, as our related work has shown (Goessling et al., 2025).

Figure 5: Scene of aerosols on 25 August 2020 at 00:00 UTC. Shown are column burdens of dust (du) in red, sea salt (ss) in blue, carbonaceous aerosol (ca) in green, and sulfuric aerosol (su) in yellow. The colormaps have a variable transparency which decreases from fully transparent at minima to fully opaque at maxima.

Table 3: Aerosol burdens, emissions, lifetimes, and optical depths at 550 nm of ICON with the HAM-lite aerosol module averaged over February 2020 to January 2021 and of AeroCom phase 3 averaged over the year 2010 (Gliß et al., 2021).

	Burden (Tg)	Emission (Tg yr ⁻¹)	Lifetime (d)	Optical depth
ICON-HAM-lite				
Dust	17.7	1993	3.2	0.009
Sea salt	15.4	4977	1.1	0.056
Carbonaceous	1.48	75.09	7.2	0.018
Sulfuric	2.55	168.7	5.5	0.032
AeroCom phase 3				
Dust	16.6	1440	3.7	0.021
Sea salt	8.7	4980	0.56	0.044
Black carbon	0.131	9.7	5.5	0.002
Organic aerosol	1.91	116.0	6.0	0.022
Sulfate	1.80	143.0	4.9	0.035

4.2 Ocean biogeochemistry components

In co-operation with the ocean biogeochemistry group in Hamburg (Prof. T. Ilyina) and the H2020 project ESM2025, ICON experiments with the additional biogeochemistry module HAMOCC were conducted (Figure 7). Marine ecosystems and fisheries are key for knowledge co-production and commercial applications in NextGEMS. The project brought together first-

Figure 6: Aerosol optical depth at 550 nm of ICON with the HAM-lite aerosol module averaged over February 2020 to January 2021 (a) and of MODIS-Aqua, i.e., the combined dark target and deep blue product (Platnick et al., 2015), averaged over 2018 to 2022 (b). The spatial average over 60° S to 60° N is given in square brackets.

time users of high-resolution model output from Senegal and France with climate modellers. An ICON ocean-only simulation forced by the observed atmospheric state showed that with fine resolution the model was able to capture key features of coastal upwelling in the sea surface, where unique observations were provided by Senegalese partners. Furthermore, a one-year coupled ICON simulation with the Cycle 4 configuration allowed to study triggering or modulation of phytoplankton blooms associated with eddies and tropical cyclones. Connecting to the fisheries application community enabled valuable discussions on specific user needs for data distribution and sharing information. Further research is presently underway and investigates storms in the Southern Ocean and their importance for carbon uptake.

Figure 7: A tropical cyclone in an ICON simulation run with ocean biogeochemistry. The time/depth plot on the right shows the evolution of the ocean’s stratification and the phytoplankton concentration—before and after the stirring through the tropical cyclone.

4.3 Novel applications arising from Knowledge Coproduction activities

To bridge the science-policy interface, the project also conducted a study to explore how the outputs of nextGEMS could be used to support national spatial planning. A case study of the Spanish energy transition was conducted, and the outputs from ICON (Hohenegger et al., 2023) and IFS-FESOM (Rackow et al., 2025) utilized, using variables of key interest to the energy sector. These variables were used for the operationalization of narrative-based storylines of renewable energy futures. The different outputs of the models allowed the study coordinators to explain climate modeling more generally to a non-technical audience, as well as the underlying differences between the models themselves (as explained in section 2.1.1 above). Thus, it contributed to the science communication and climate literacy efforts of the project, whilst providing a novel application through the mix of storyline approaches (Baulenas et al., 2025).

Figure 8: Timeseries of global-mean temperature and top-of-atmosphere radiation balance in nextGEMS simulations, reanalysis (ERA5) and observations (CERES-EBAF). (Top), annual-mean 2m temperature [K] in the production future scenario simulation (green line), and in the newly performed historical simulation (orange line) covering the period 1990–2019, compared to the reference from ERA5 reanalysis. (Bottom), TOA radiation balance in simulations and reanalysis/observations. Colors follow the top panel.

5 Longer simulations of the observational period 1990-2019

To allow for an overlap with the observational period and as requested from the nextGEMS community, historical simulations at 9 km in the atmosphere and 5 km in the ocean have been performed for the period 1990-2019 with IFS-FESOM (Rackow et al., 2025). These simulations are complementary to the 30-year scenario simulations in nextGEMS for the period 2020–2049 (Segura et al., 2025), with identical settings.

Figure 8 (top panel) shows how the global annual-mean 2m temperature timeseries evolves in the newly performed historical simulation and in the future scenario with IFS-FESOM, compared to the present-day reference from the ERA5 reanalysis. The future scenario simulation is on the higher end of warming responses known from climate models showing a positive low-cloud feedback. The historical simulation puts this warming into context, showing a slight warming after 20 years of coupled simulation compared to ERA5 over the historical period. Whether the offset in the decade 2010–2019 is within the uncertainty range of the observations, accounting for interannual and decadal variability of the climate system, or partially indicating a coupled model drift is still under investigation. The former reason would confirm the strong warming response in IFS-FESOM to greenhouse gas forcing, while the latter reason could imply that the warming response may need to be corrected downwards.

In terms of top-of-the-atmosphere radiation balance, from Figure 8 (bottom panel) we can see an overall very good fit of IFS-FESOM to ERA5 and CERES-EBAF satellite observations, including a realistic signal from the Pinatubo eruption in 1991. However, the timescale of surface warming appears to be too fast in IFS-FESOM between 2010-2019, with the model potentially responding too quickly to atmospheric forcing. The model may thus tend to a more balanced (warmer) surface state too quickly instead of generating an increasing radiation imbalance at the TOA, as in observations from CERES-EBAF. Again, this may have implications for how to interpret the warming response in the future scenario.

Figure 9: Timeseries of global-mean 2-metre temperature (in Kelvin units) for the ICON historical run produced in phase 1 of Destination Earth, within the Climate Adaptation Digital Twin. The monthly mean reanalysis ERA5 historical 2-metre temperature is shown by the dashed black line with the standard deviation showed in grey shade. Figure produced by the simulation monitoring and evaluating tool for Destination Earth AQUA.

Figure 10: Composition of several variables over a particular tropical cyclone developing in the 2.8km simulations by IFS-FESOM with reduced cloud-base mass flux (RCBMF). On the top row, from left to right: sea surface temperature, 10-meter wind gust, relative humidity at 700 hPa, surface latent heat flux. On the bottom row, from left to right: 2-meter temperature, total precipitation rate, vertical velocity at 850 hPa and outgoing longwave radiation at top of the atmosphere.

For ICON, a comparable historical simulation has been performed (Fig 9) in the context of the DestinE initiative that is available via the [DestinE platform](#) to nextGEMS partners. For both ICON and IFS-FESOM, the developments and testing performed throughout the course of nextGEMS have led to consolidated model versions that have fed the Destination Earth's [Climate Adaptation Digital Twin](#). Within this initiative, [simulations](#) of historical period (1990-2020), future scenarios following SSP3-7.0 (2020-2040), control 1990 simulations and [storylines](#) have been carried at resolutions of 10 and 5 km-s with models and configurations based on those developed within nextGEMS.

6 Multi-annual 2.5 km coupled simulations

Regarding the spatial resolution and accounting for the granted availability of computational resources at the DKRZ, towards the end of the project we have pushed the spatial resolution to 2.5 km, running several 14-month simulations with ICON (AMIP) and with IFS-FESOM (AMIP and coupled TCo3999 atmosphere with NG5 ocean grid). Three distinct simulations were completed for IFS-FESOM: (1) a fully coupled configuration using a reduced cloud base mass flux (RCBMF) (Figure 10), (2) a coupled configuration with deep convection disabled entirely, and (3) an AMIP-style IFS simulation at 2.8 km, also using RCBMF. All simulations are started on the 1st of January 2020 and run for 14 months, ending on 1st of March, 2021.

Results with IFS-FESOM show that even at 2.8 km resolution, the disadvantages of deactivating the deep convection scheme outweigh the advantages: large biases still exist, among others, in precipitation characteristics that affect vertical temperature distributions and consequently the large-scale circulation. This motivates both a further development of the convection scheme targeting km-scale resolutions, and of the microphysics, to enable more realistic characteristics also in the absence of a convection scheme.

Output data on the HEALPix grid from the 2.5 km nextGEMS simulations with ICON and IFS-FESOM were prepared also for the [global 'HK25' hackathon](#), with a focus on accessibility and standardization. The data are available via the [online catalogue](#). The HK25 hackathon took place in May 2025 and was a major international effort to explore the capabilities of ultra-high-resolution Earth system simulations. Organised by the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP), the event brought together climate scientists, data engineers, and Earth system modellers to experiment with cutting-edge datasets and workflows and explore km-scale simulations from [10 different modelling systems](#), including the two nextGEMS models ICON and IFS-FESOM. Additional to the atmosphere-only simulation for the global hackathon, also a three year coupled simulation was performed on LUMI with ICON using EuroHPC resources available to nextGEMS through an extreme scale access call under grant number EHPC-EXT-2023E02-077.

7 Conclusion

For this deliverable, no changes from the original plan need to be reported.

The deliverable lists selected model developments that go beyond sensitivities to spatial resolution. We draw conclusions on their potential for further improving the SR-ESMs in nextGEMS, ICON (Hohenegger et al., 2023) and IFS-FESOM (Rackow et al., 2025). We have covered parameterised aspects (turbulent mixing in atmosphere and ocean, tuning of micro-physics) and developments aimed at expanding the scope of what is being modelled (simple aerosol models, biogeochemistry components, and novel applications arising from Knowledge Coproduction activities).

We also present new nextGEMS simulations (at 9 km resolution) that overlap with the observational period, and that have identical settings to the future scenario production simulations in Cycle 4, which had been suggested by the nextGEMS partners. Moreover, the recent availability of the new storm-resolving 2.5 km datasets of shorter duration, but still of multi-annual duration (as many 14 months runs have been performed), should benefit the analyses of the nextGEMS community. In particular, these novel simulations will support analyses that may not be possible to be addressed to full extent with the 9 km production simulations performed in Cycle 4, despite their much longer length of 30 years.

Technical efforts for preparing IFS-FESOM data for the HK25 hackathon included exploring tools by the German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ) that are typically used for rewriting and rechunking ICON data in space and time into Zarr format. We also aligned the IFS variable naming and units with CF conventions. As a result, alongside ICON data, dedicated atmosphere

and ocean data from IFS-FESOM are now available to global hackathon participants via both the EERIE cloud and the DKRZ S3 cloud infrastructure. With over 600 participants collaborating across 10 locations worldwide and engaging in both local activities and global exchange sessions, a wide range of scientific outcomes can be anticipated from HK25. While the specific results are still emerging, the expectation is that the hackathon may yield valuable insights over time. The well-prepared and standardized datasets are expected to be beneficial, as it facilitates inclusion of ICON and IFS-FESOM in many of the planned model intercomparison studies.

With the ICON model version that was developed as part of nextGEMS, we are now aiming to further expand the model's scope since we could successfully simulate a stable climate. A computing proposal was approved where the goal is to conduct a 1-year ICON simulation, including carbon cycle, at a grid spacing of 1.25 km, making use of the new exascale supercomputer JUPITER. The proposal is called "Exascale-enabled Scale and Process Interactions in the Earth System" and was recently approved (application number 60830) as part of the GCS Exascale Pioneer Project.

Furthermore, a relevant outcome of nextGEMS and the development of the SR-ESM is that these feed into the Destination Earth Climate Adaptation Digital Twin. This digital twin combines cutting-edge global Earth-system models, impact-sector applications and observations into a unified framework, leveraging the world-leading supercomputing facilities of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking. As a result, this Digital Twin provides global climate projections and impact-sector information on multi-decadal timescales, between 1990 and 2050, at very high spatial resolutions (5 to 10 km).

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